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THE ASSESSMENT OF THE SCIENTIFIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE UG EMPLOYEES

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The basis for assessing the achievements of research workers for individual disciplines

	Archeology	Economics and finance	Philosophy	Social and economic geography and spatial management	History	Computer and information sciences	Linguistics	Literary studies	Mathematics	Biological sciences	Chemical sciences	Physical sciences	Security studies	Culture and religion studies	Communication and media studies	political science and public administration	Arts studies	Management and quality studies	Earth and related environmental sciences	Sociology	Law	Education	Psychology	Biotechnology	Polish studies
WoS	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Scopus	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
ERIH Plus	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓					✓ ³	✓ ⁴	✓ ³	✓ ³	✓	✓		✓	✓				✓
Monographs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Other		✓ ¹									✓ ²		✓ ¹	✓ ⁵		✓ ⁵	✓ ⁵	✓ ¹							

¹scientific projects

²patents

³or CEJSH

⁴ or AIO, Latinindex, RBN, RGB, CEJSH, CEEOL, ICI Journal List

⁵ chapter in a monograph

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Does the scientific discipline take into account the scientist's level of experience and the scientific title?

	Archeology	Economics and finance	Philosophy	Social and economic geography and spatial management	History	Computer and information sciences	Linguistics	Literary studies	Mathematics	Biological sciences	Chemical sciences	Physical sciences	Security studies	Culture and religion studies	Communication and media studies	Political science and public administration	Arts studies	Management and quality studies	Earth and related environmental sciences	Sociology	Law	Education	Psychology	Biotechnology	Polish studies
Yes/No	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES

A – Article (WoS, Scopus....)

M – Monograph

C – Chapter in a monograph

> greater than

≥ greater than or equal to

∧ conjunction (and)

∨ alternative (or)

*a) it has been published in a publishing house from the highest level of the publishing house list, b) it has received an award granted by the Prime Minister, the Minister of Education and Science, a unit of the Polish Academy of Sciences, the Foundation for Polish Science, a scientific society or another of high prestige in the scientific discipline, c) it has been placed in foreign libraries in at least five countries according to the Worldcat, RNB or RGB catalogues;

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> greater than

≥ greater than or equal to

^ conjunction (and)

v alternative (or)

*P-project

Social Sciences:

COMMUNICATION AND MEDIA STUDIES

Research and
academic group $\geq 4A$ $\geq 1M \wedge 1A$ $\geq 2M \wedge 1A$ $\geq 1M \wedge 1A \wedge 1C$ $\geq 2C \wedge \geq 2A$

Research group

 $\geq 6A$ $\geq 4A \wedge \geq 1M$

A – Article (WoS, Scopus....)

M – Monograph

C – Chapter in a monograph

> greater than

≥ greater than or equal to

∧ conjunction (and)

∨ alternative (or)

A=M, Article could be exchange for a monograph

A=P, Article could be exchange for patent

